

Not All Triangles Are Equilateral:

Making the Case for Explicit Initial Teacher Education to Equip Newly-Qualified Teachers to Work Effectively with Parents with a Focus on Educational Disadvantage.

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Abstract:

Since the 1990s, education policy in Ireland has emphasised the role that the family plays in a child's educational attainment; successive Governments' focus on educational disadvantage is evident through various initiatives including the Breaking the Cycle programme of 1996 and the current Delivering Equality of Education in Schools 2017 Plan. Extra financial and staffing supports have been offered to targeted schools to ensure better educational outcomes for the children who attend. However, a critical aspect that warrants further investigation is the need for initial teacher education programmes to provide specific and explicit tutoring to equip future teachers to effectively engage with families. *Céim: The Standards for Initial Teacher Education* (The Teaching Council, 2020) requires that higher-education institutions provide student teachers with the skills and knowledge to work effectively with families but this has yet to be a part of every initial teacher education providers' curriculum. This proposed study sets out to explore the readiness and preparedness of newly qualified teachers to work with families, especially those from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds. Drawing both from educational and sociological research, this proposed study will explore the attitudes of newly qualified teachers and primary principals towards how confident and able newly qualified teachers are to work with families from diverse socio-economic backgrounds.

Keywords

Initial Teacher Education; Newly Qualified Teachers; Parents; Delivering Opportunities for Equality in Schools; DEIS; Educational Disadvantage.

Three key highlights

- Newly-qualified teachers (NQTs) enter the classroom not fully prepared to work effectively with parents and families.
- Parents and families from socially- and educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds require different supports to become engaged in their children's education than those from higher socio-economic backgrounds.
- This proposed study sets out to explore how specific and explicit focus on working effectively with parents and families both during initial teacher education and NQT induction could benefit early-career teachers in their practice.

Introduction

“Educational achievement is strongly related to socio-economic status.

So too is [family engagement] in education” (Desforges and Abouchar, 2003, p. 32).

Few professions place as much pressure on their newest recruits as teaching, “the profession that eats its young” (Halford, 1998, p. 33). Kearney (2014) observes that newly-qualified teachers (NQTs) enter their classrooms and assume the same professional responsibilities as their more experienced colleagues. This extends beyond the core task of delivering quality teaching and learning and towards the building of effective relationships with the families of the children they teach. Céim: The Standards for Initial Teacher Education (Teaching Council, 2020) requires that higher-education institutions provide student teachers with the skills and knowledge to work effectively with families but this is yet to be explicitly

delivered across all initial teacher education (ITE) curricula in Ireland. From an educational disadvantage perspective, the different lived experiences of early-career teachers and the children they teach also merits investigation, especially within schools which have Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS) status. While the literature typically refers to ‘parental involvement’, the remainder of this minor paper will use the term ‘family engagement’ and the reasons for this are described below. This proposed study sets out to explore the need for direct and explicit teacher education for students, teachers and professional learning (PL) for NQTs on this topic based on the lived experiences of NQTs as they start to teach, specifically with regards to educational disadvantage.

Rationale

This paper’s title comes from Coleman’s (1998) research into parent, child and teacher collaboration; the child sits at the top of the triangle and is supported by their family and school. Coleman’s version of this family-school relationship is rooted in equality in the parent-teacher relationship; it promotes a shared purpose, responsibility and respect.

However, as this paper’s title proposes, not all triangles are equilateral: the same can be said for the balance between family-school relationships. As a Doctorate of Education student, I have identified that herein lies a problem of practice; my positionality as a teacher and principal in a DEIS Band-1 primary school and as an ITE lecturer identifies two key factors that influence this imbalance in Coleman’s home-school triangle. Firstly, NQTs should be better prepared to effectively work with parents and families. Secondly, they require a better understanding of the lived-experiences of the families they work with, especially with families from educationally-disadvantaged settings.

In Ireland, the term ‘educational disadvantage’ refers to a range of inter-generational barriers which may impact upon children from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds the

opportunities to succeed in school (Harford, 2018). These barriers include poverty, poor health, inadequate housing and limited access to educational resources and opportunities (Todd, 2007). These can have a cumulative effect over time and contribute to a widening achievement gap between children from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds and their more advantaged peers (Jeynes, 2005). Current national education policy addressing educational disadvantage in Ireland is the DEIS Plan (Department of Education and Skills, 2017). In acknowledgement of the role of the family in a child's education, the seventh of the DEIS Plan's eight targets aims to improve the level of parental engagement in their school communities through school planning. The use of the word 'engagement' in the current DEIS plan is remarkable as the DEIS Action Plan (2005) required schools to place emphasis on parental 'involvement' (DES, 2005, p, 3); while parental/family involvement usually refers to attending school-based events or programmes, parental/family engagement describes a parental/family ownership of the child's education (Pushor, 2015; Ryan and Lannin, 2021). This suggests a shift in education policy goals to creating meaningful partnership between school and home for families from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds; this shift will be unpacked further in this paper. For the remainder of this paper, the terms 'family' and 'families' will be used in place of 'parent' and 'parental'. This is a specific choice and the rationale for this is due to the interchangeability of these terms in literature.

As part of my doctoral studies to date, I conducted a critical policy analysis of the DEIS 2017 Plan. My findings observe that there is more to delivering the DEIS 2017 Plan than that which lies within its text, especially with regards to developing teachers' capacity for family engagement. To expand on this, Lipsky's theory of 'street-level bureaucrats' comes to the fore; policy, whatever its genesis, is interpreted on the ground by those who enact it (1980). Or indeed, that policy is subject to "interpretations of interpretations" (Rizvi and Kemmis, 1987, p. 14). Furthermore, it interrogates whether the policy gets interpreted as intended.

Lastly, it acknowledges that practitioners are active agents who are active in the context of practice and not merely recipients of policy. As stated by Bowe, Ball and Gold, “[p]ractitioners do not confront policy texts as naïve readers, they come with histories, with experiences, with values and purposes of their own, they have interests in the meaning of policy” (1992, p. 22). While NQTs enter teaching with their own histories, values and purposes, these are not necessarily professionally-based and therefore, support is required to enable early-career stage teachers to interpret and enact policy as the creators intended. The DEIS Plan (Department of Education and Skills, 2017) recognises the particular needs of children from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds; to better balance Coleman’s family-school triangle that this paper’s title refers to, this proposed study sets out to examine if NQTs require further supports to be able to work effectively with families.

Theoretical Framework

“Come off it, Diane, you’d get fed up never having enough money, worrying about bills. You try it” (Reay, 2000, p. 581).

From birth until to 6th year (final year of formal education; 17/18 years of age), children in Ireland spend 15% of their waking hours in school (Irish National Teachers Organisation, 1997). This underscores the importance of the educational support that a child receives at home; it has been long-recognised that meaningful partnership between family and school is an indicator of educational success; (Lareau, 1989; Conaty, 2002; Hanafin and Lynch, 2002; Crozier and Reay, 2005; Epstein, 2018; Fleming and Harford, 2021).

Figure 1 is an adaptation of Coleman's collaboration triangle (1998). It depicts the equal supporting roles played by families and schools in supporting the child to experience educational success. It replaces 'parent' for 'family' as per the rationale offered above.

Fig. 1. Adapted from Coleman, 1998

Figure 1 above illustrates an adapted version of Coleman's theory of the importance of the family/school relationship in supporting a child's education. This collaborative model suggests an equity that does not always exist as it does not take into consideration the capacity of families from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds to be enfranchised to play their part in education. Such capacity is impacted upon by Rittel and Webber's (1973) identification of 'wicked problems'; they include, but are not limited to, low adult literacy and numeracy levels, poverty, unsuitable housing, anti-social behaviour and addiction issues (Fleming and Harford 2021). What also should be considered are the historical perceptions and attitudes of schools and teachers which often lacked an understanding of the lives of families from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds and therefore perpetuated intergenerational educational disadvantage (Bourdieu, 1986; Lareau, 1989; Reay, 2000; Boldt, 2000; Hanafin and Lynch, 2002).

This lack of understanding is explored in Boldt's 2000 study of teachers' attitudes and perceptions of educational disadvantage. Judgemental statements were made, such as "some parents do not even bother" and that "the underclass of Dublin is a harsh place that represents no beauty and no gentleness" (p. 15). As observed by Kellaghan (2002), the deep-seated cultural values that a middle class teacher brings to a DEIS school classroom continue to provide a mis-match to those of the families of the children being taught; clashes between

school and home can be caused due to a lack of understanding from the school. Therefore, to avoid such frustrations, student teachers should be explicitly taught how to effectively work with families from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds.

In the opening quote of this section, ‘Jalil’ describes the guilt and frustrations she feels when she cannot fully engage with her child’s education (Reay, 2000). This contrasts with another mother interviewed in the same study who takes her children to eat out two or three times a week to help them develop social skills. The contrast between these mothers’ lived experiences and engagement with their children’s education can be viewed through the lens of Bourdieu’s forms of capital (1986). This is key to this proposed study as it explores the non-monetary characteristics of capital and interrogates their wider sociological aspects; these are particularly applicable to educational disadvantage. To briefly explore Bourdieu’s theories of forms of capital, in its traditional economic sense, capital can be defined as an individual’s financial wealth; some people have more money than others and the more a person has, the more comfortable life that person can live. Bourdieu defines capital in this sense as "accumulated labour which [...] enables [individuals] to appropriate social energy in the form of reified or living labour" (1986, p. 241). In deconstructing this definition of capital, he develops alternative forms of capital, namely economic, cultural and social. Examining family engagement in education from a social class perspective, it is by observing the levels at which these alternative capitals are accumulated and possessed by families that grant a deeper insight into the relationship between socio-economic status and educational success.

It also highlights the need for an understanding and recognition at policy level of the “capacity” for family engagement in education; those which include and extend beyond economic capital. One reason why “all too often relationships between parents and teachers

are defined by their inequitable nature” (Crozier & Reay, 2005, p. 157) can be explained by the link between social class and parental involvement. This alternate theory of capital informs this study’s central research question; namely, are NQTs as prepared as they should be to work in DEIS settings.

Proposed Methods

The following research questions would be asked:

- What are the lived experiences of NQTs as they start to teach, specifically with regards to educational disadvantage?
- What are NQTs’ attitudes towards their ability and confidence in working with families?
- What are the principal's attitudes to NQTs’ abilities and confidence in working with families?

At this early stage, this proposed study’s methods are a sequential explanatory study employing a mixed-methods design. Its sampling frame would consist of NQTs in their second year of teaching and their principals, with recruitment based on pre-study permission to contact student teachers who are currently in their final year of ITE. This will be followed up with post-ethics approval with all relevant documentation, including consent forms and a plain language statement. The initial stage of the data gathering consists of a survey to be followed by an invitation to attend focus groups. As yet-to-be determined stratification variables will be applied to further examine the topic through focus group research.

Ethical Considerations

While the proposed study participants are not considered vulnerable, no study can be deemed free from ethical considerations. It is not envisaged that the topic or methods employed will elicit any significant difficulties or risks for the participants but included in the consent form will be details of additional support for participants should they experience adverse effects from their inclusion in the study. The plain language statement will inform all participants that all efforts ensure anonymity and confidentiality will be made, that they are not required to answer all or any questions and that participants have the right to withdraw from the research at any time.

Conclusion

This proposed study sets out to explore NQTs' self-recognition of readiness to work effectively with parents from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds. It is, at its core, an examination of what happens 'when policy hits the tar' and the need to align education policy with the realities of life in DEIS classrooms. By exploring the attitudes of NQTs and principals, this proposed study will peripherally road-test the context of practice for three current educational policy texts, namely Céim, Droichead and the DEIS Plan. It will also identify possible future trajectories within these policies as they relate to better equipping NQTs to work effectively with parents, especially those from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds. At this juncture, it might be prudent to identify some such potential trajectories and potential implications for practice and policy:

- This proposed study may lead to a description of the explicit initial teacher education required to better equip student teachers to work effectively with families from educationally-disadvantaged backgrounds.

- As identified by Gorman and Furlong (2023), the Teaching Council seeks stronger ITE provider-school partnerships in the area of student placement. This could provide opportunities for student teachers to experience working with families while building their in-the-field element of their education. However, this is contingent on schools having the resources, support and motivation to do so. Also identified in this study is the onus placed on ITE providers to build such partnerships while schools are only encouraged to do so, even though schools are the institutions where student teachers will be employed in the future.
- Further research might be relevant in the field of teacher induction and how targeted professional learning for NQTs in the area of working with families from educationally-disadvantaged families could be of benefit as part of the Droichead teacher induction process.

While not exhaustive, the above possible trajectories indicate the potential influence this proposed study may have upon practice, policy and research to help balance Coleman's home-school triangle in the context of educational disadvantage. While not all triangles are equilateral, we can view some of them as more balanced than before by creatively sizing them up from different angles.

References

Boldt, Scott. (2000) *Powerful hopes: an in-depth study of the potential of young people from the inner city of Dublin*. Dublin: Marino Institute of Education.

Bourdieu, P. (1986) *Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education*, New York: Greenwood Press

Bowe, R., Ball, S. J. and Gold, A. (1992) *Reforming education and changing schools*. London: Routledge.

Coleman, P. (1998) *Parent, student and teacher collaboration the power of three*. London: Paul Chapman.

Conaty, Concepta. (2002) *Including all: home, school and community united in education*. Dublin: Veritas.

Crozier, G. and Reay, D. (2005) *Parents and schools; partners or protagonists?* Stoke-on-Trent: Trentham

Department of Education (2005) *DEIS Action Plan 2005*. Available at <https://assets.gov.ie/24465/40677432ed49418d8c27bfb524f12a7b.pdf> (Accessed: 9 February 2023).

Department of Education (2017) *DEIS Plan 2017*. Available at: <https://www.gov.ie/pdf/?file=https://assets.gov.ie/24451/ba1553e873864a559266d344b4c78660.pdf#page=null> (Accessed: 9 February 2023).

Desforges, C. and Abouchar, A. (2003) *The impact of parental involvement, parental support and family education on pupil achievements and adjustment: a literature review*. Nottingham: Department for Education and Skills Publications.

Epstein, J. L. (2018). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. London: Routledge

Fleming, B. and Harford, J. (2021) 'The DEIS programme as a policy aimed at combating educational disadvantage: fit for purpose?', *Irish Educational Studies*, 0(0), pp. 1–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2021.1964568>.

Gorman, A. and Furlong, C. (2023) 'Partnership or prescription: a critical discourse analysis of HEI-school partnership policy in the Republic of Ireland', *Asia-Pacific journal of teacher*

education, 51(2), pp. 198–212. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1359866X.2023.2177139>.

Halford, J. M. (1998). 'Easing the way for new teachers', *Educational Leadership*, 55, 33–36

Hanafin, J. and Lynch, A. (2002) 'Peripheral voices: parental involvement, social class, and educational disadvantage', *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 23. pp. 35–49.

Irish National Teachers' Organisation (INTO) (1997). *Parental involvement: possibilities for partnership*. Dublin: INTO.

Jeynes, W. H. (2005). 'The effects of parental involvement on the academic achievement of African American youth. *Journal of Negro Education*, 74(3), pp. 260–274.

Kellaghan, T. (2002) *Preparing teachers for the 21st century : report of the working group on primary preservice teacher education*. Dublin: Stationery Office.

Lynch, K. (1999) *Equality in education*. Dublin: Gill & Macmillan

Lipsky, M (1980) *Street-level Bureaucracy: The Dilemmas of the Individual in Public Services*. New York: Russell Sage Foundation.

Pushor, D. and Parent Engagement Collaborative. (2015) *Living as mapmakers: charting a course with children guided by parent knowledge*. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers

Rittel, H.W.J. and Webber, M.M. (1973) 'Dilemmas in a general theory of planning', *Policy Sci* 4, pp. 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01405730>

Rizvi, F. and Kemmis, S. (1987) *Dilemmas of reform*. Deakin University Press, Geelong.

Ryan, S. and Lannin, C. (2021) *Parents in partnership: mapping the way for family, school and community engagement*. Curriculum Development Unit: Limerick

Reay, D. (2000) 'A useful extension of Bourdieu's conceptual framework?: emotional capital as a way of understanding mothers' involvement in their children's education?', *The Sociological Review*, 48(4), pp. 568–585. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-954X.00233>.

The Teaching Council (2017) *Droichead: the integrated professional induction framework.* Maynooth: The Teaching Council.

The Teaching Council (2020) *Céim: the standards for initial teacher education.* Maynooth: The Teaching Council.

Todd, L. (2007) *Partnerships for Inclusive Education: a critical approach to collaborative working*, Oxon: Routledge Falmer.